

Sex differences in the longitudinal association between physical functioning and cognitive decline: A 20-year cohort study in Central Europe

Short title: Women, Physical Function, and Cognition

Tatyana Court¹, Andrea Dalecká¹, Naděžda Čapková², Hynek Pikhart^{1,3}, Martin Bobák^{1,3}

¹RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

²National Institute of Public Health, Prague, Czech Republic

³Research Department of Epidemiology and Public Health, University College London, London, UK

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Corresponding author / Reprint request:

T. Court, MD, PhD

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Brno, Czech Republic

Koltarska 2, 625 00 Brno, Czech Republic

Tel. (+420) 732 159 179, E-mail: tatyana.court@recetox.muni.cz

Abstract

Background: The relationship between physical functioning (PF) and cognitive decline remains inconsistent, with sex differences underexplored. This study examined whether baseline PF predicts cognitive decline over 20 years with sex-specific associations in a Central European population.

Methods: A prospective cohort study of 1,143 participants (mean age 55.1±6.4 years, 60.5% women) from the Czech HAPIEE study was analysed. PF was defined from a validated 23-item tool including activities of daily living, grip strength, functional limitations, and physical activity. Cognitive function was assessed at baseline and 20-year follow-up using standardised cognitive tests. The primary outcome was a lower cognition defined as follow-up global score below the baseline sample median. Sex-stratified logistic regression estimated odds ratios (OR) for hierarchical models adjusted for age, baseline cognition, sociodemographic and clinical covariates. Inverse probability weighting (IPW) addressed selective attrition.

Results: At follow-up, 654 participants (57.2%) had lower cognition. Associations between PF and cognition differed by sex. In women, poorer PF predicted lower cognition with higher odds in a dose-response pattern. After adjustment for age and baseline cognition, the OR for low versus robust PF was 2.04 (95% CI 1.22 to 3.41). Similar findings were observed in incident case analysis (low PF: OR 1.87 (95% CI 1.03 to 3.40)). This trend persisted after full adjustment and IPW, although estimates did not reach statistical significance. Results were consistent across sensitivity analyses. In men, no consistent association was found.

Conclusions: Lower PF at midlife was associated with cognitive decline over 20-year follow-up in women but not in men. Multidomain PF assessment may help identify women at risk of cognitive decline, supporting sex-specific approaches in dementia research and prevention.

Key words: Cognitive decline; Physical Functioning; Sex difference; Aging; Longitudinal study; Dementia prevention.

Introduction

The prevalence of dementia is projected to increase from 57 million cases in 2019 to 153 million by 2050, with healthcare costs expected to exceed \$16.9 trillion^{1,2}. Central and Eastern European populations have high cardiovascular disease burdens, which are established risk factors for dementia^{3,4}. Identifying early, modifiable risk factors decades prior to dementia diagnosis is a public health priority.

Physical functioning (PF), including mobility, strength, and activities of daily living (ADL), has been associated with cognitive decline^{5,6}. Large prospective cohorts indicate that slower gait speed and weaker grip strength predict dementia⁷⁻¹¹. Multidomain indices combining objective performance with functional limitations may explain cognitive risk better than single measures^{10,11}.

Several mechanisms link PF to cognition. Shared vascular pathways, chronic inflammation, and neurotrophic signaling through brain-derived neurotrophic factor affect simultaneously muscular and neural systems¹²⁻¹⁴. However, the temporal relationship remains unclear. Some studies report that PF decline precedes cognitive decline⁷⁻¹¹, while others report bidirectional associations in which cognitive impairment predicts later functional limitations^{5,6}. This reciprocal relation is a challenge for causal interpretation, especially in studies with short follow-up where prodromal dementia may influence both domains¹⁵.

Sex-specific patterns require further investigation. Women have more functional limitations yet longer life expectancy¹⁶. Cognitive trajectories differ by sex, with women showing better midlife performance but potentially steeper late-life decline¹⁷. Biological mechanisms, including endocrine changes around menopause and subsequent estrogen decline show sex-specific patterns in the associations between PF and cognition^{18,19}. Existing evidence provides mixed results, with some studies reporting stronger associations between PF and cognition among women but not in others^{15,17,20,21}.

In earlier cross-sectional analyses of the Health, Alcohol and Psychosocial factors In Eastern Europe (HAPIEE) cohort, associations between PF and cognition were stronger in women than in men²². Whether these differences translate into long-term predictive associations remains unclear. Cross-sectional studies cannot determine the direction of associations and are especially susceptible to reverse causation.

To address these limitations, this study used longitudinal data to investigate whether PF predicts cognitive decline over 20 years and whether associations differ by sex in the Czech arm of the HAPIEE cohort.

Methods

Study design and participants

This study used prospective data from the Czech arm of the HAPIEE cohort⁴. The HAPIEE study enrolled participants aged 45–69 years through population registries in seven urban centres. Baseline data on demographics, health status, medical examination findings, lifestyle, socioeconomic factors, and psychosocial variables were collected during 2002–2005 through face-to-face computer-assisted personal interviews combined with clinical examinations.

For this prospective analysis, data from the baseline survey and the 2024 follow-up cognitive assessment were used. The analysis was limited to the Czech cohort, as follow-up cognitive testing was only conducted in Czechia. Participants were included if they had complete data on PF and cognitive tests at baseline, participated in follow-up assessment, and had non-missing data for relevant covariates. Of those without follow-up cognitive assessment, approximately 50% had died before the 2024 follow-up (Figure 1). The final analytic sample include 1143 participants.

Measurement of Physical Functioning

Baseline PF was assessed using a validated 23-item PFS developed in earlier work²². The score covers four domains:

- (1) ADL/IADL: ten items on loss of independence, including feeding, dressing, bed mobility, toileting, cooking, shopping, telephone use, medication use, financial management, and fine motor tasks.
- (2) Grip strength: measured with a Scandidact dynamometer using sex-specific cut-offs for none, mild, and major impairment.
- (3) Functional limitations: ten items assessing limitations in lifting, stair climbing, bending, kneeling, stooping, and walking short or moderate distances.
- (4) Physical activity: self-reported levels classified by WHO thresholds²³ (≥ 150 min/week moderate or ≥ 75 min/week vigorous), divided into tertiles.

Each item was coded 0 (no deficit), 0.5 (partial deficit), or 1 (deficit), and the PFS was computed as the

proportion of deficits across the 23 items²². Higher PFS values reflect a greater proportion of deficits and therefore poorer PF. In earlier study, PF was grouped into five categories: robust ($PFS \leq 0.03$), good ($PFS > 0.03 - 0.07$), moderate ($PFS > 0.07 - 0.14$), low ($PFS > 0.14 - 0.21$), and very low ($PFS > 0.21$)²².

For the primary exposure in this analysis, the low and very low categories were combined ($PFS > 0.14$) due to small sample sizes in sex-stratified models and limited stability of estimates. The analyses showed no improvement in the fit in model with five vs. four categories, so the five-level version was used only in sensitivity analyses.

Outcome

Cognitive function was assessed using tests adapted from the Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's Disease (CERAD)²⁴, including:

- (1) Verbal memory: immediate and delayed recall of a 10-word list;
- (2) Verbal fluency: number of animals named in one minute;
- (3) Processing speed and concentration: letter cancellation task identifying target letters P and W within one minute.

Scores were standardized (z-scores, mean 0, SD 1), and a global cognitive score was defined as the mean of the three test z-scores.

The primary outcome was lower cognition at follow-up, defined as a follow-up global cognitive score below the baseline median. Secondary outcomes were continuous global cognition at follow-up and incident lower cognition among participants with baseline cognition at or above the median.

Covariates

Covariates were selected based on known associations with PF and cognitive aging, available data, correlations identified in univariate analysis and were further refined using the least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO) regression in our previous study²². Baseline variables included: age, sex, education level (primary, secondary, vocational, university), occupation (employed, retired employed, retired unemployed, unemployed), deprivation scale (1–12), smoking status (never, current, past), alcohol consumption (never to ≥ 5 drinks/week), stroke, myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease, hypertension (blood pressure $> 140/90$ mmHg and/or treated hypertension), diabetes, asthma, chronic obstructive

pulmonary disease, and depression (CES-D score ≥ 16)²⁵. Body mass index was calculated from measured weight and height and categorized according to WHO recommendations.

Statistical analyses

Baseline characteristics were summarized according to cognitive outcome status at follow-up using means and standard deviations for continuous variables and counts and percentages for categorical variables. Standardized differences were calculated to assess imbalance; standardized difference >0.10 indicates meaningful difference. To further explore potential bias, baseline characteristics were also compared between men and women within outcome categories. We additionally performed an attrition analysis comparing baseline characteristics of participants included in the follow-up versus those lost to follow-up (Supplementary figure 1). This assessment is presented in Tables 1-2 and Supplementary Table 1.

The association between PF and lower cognition was analyzed using logistic regression with robust PF category as reference. Odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI) were estimated for hierarchical models:

(1) Model 1: adjusted for age (and sex in pooled analyses)

(2) Model 2: Model 1 plus baseline cognition adjustment (continuous global cognitive score, incorporating quadratic terms and restricted cubic splines for baseline cognition did not improve model fit), testing whether PF predicts cognitive change over 20 years independently of cognitive decline already present at midlife.

(3) Model 3: Model 2 plus reduced multivariable adjustment (occupation, education, alcohol, smoking, BMI, hypertension, diabetes, and asthma).

(4) Model 4: Model 3 with inverse probability weighting (IPW) to account for attrition.

The main multivariable model used reduced adjustment to maintain model stability and precision while controlling for major confounding domains (sociodemographic position, health behaviors, chronic conditions). Fully adjusted models (additionally including myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease,

stroke, depression) were examined in sensitivity analyses.

Given strong sex differences (p for sex heterogeneity = 0.02) in the association between PF and cognition observed in previous study, all primary analyses were stratified by sex²². Pooled analyses were conducted to test for heterogeneity.

IPW was used to reduce bias from selective follow-up²⁶. Logistic regression modeled probability of follow-up participation based on baseline predictors. Stabilized weights were estimated separately for each sex stratum, trimmed at 1st and 99th percentiles, and applied in weighted logistic regression models using robust standard errors (Supplementary figure 4).

Multiple sensitivity analyses verified robustness: (1) incident lower cognition (restricted to subjects with baseline cognition above median); (2) continuous outcomes (linear regression); (3) alternative cut-point (follow-up median); (4) continuous PF (per SD increase); (5) five-category PF exposure; (6) full covariate adjustment.

All statistical analyses were performed using STATA (Version 17, College Station, TX).

Results

Baseline characteristics of study participants

The baseline Czech HAPIEE sample included 4,396 participants. Follow-up cognitive assessment was available for 1,143 participants (26%) and 50% of participants were dead at the time of the follow-up re-examination. Compared with participants without follow-up, those retained were younger at baseline (55.1 vs 59.6 years), more often women (60.5% vs 52.7%), had better baseline global cognitive function (0.33 vs 0.03) (Supplementary table 1). They had a higher baseline PF with a higher proportion classified as Robust (31.3% vs 23.1%) and a lower proportion classified as Low (21.7% vs 33.5%) (Supplementary figure 2) and had a more favorable socioeconomic and health profile, including higher education, employment rates, and lower prevalence of obesity, hypertension, and depression. (Supplementary table 1). These differences

supported the use of IPW to address selective follow-up.

Among participants with follow-up cognitive assessment (N = 1,143), those classified with lower cognition at follow-up (N = 654) were older (56.8 vs. 52.7 years) and more likely to be men (48.2% vs. 28.0%, $p < 0.001$) than those with higher cognition (Table 1, Supplementary figure 3). Lower cognition was associated with lower educational attainment (university degree: 15.1% vs. 27.0%), higher rates of non-employment among pensioners (31.0% vs. 13.7%), and a less favourable health profile, with higher prevalence of obesity (23.5% vs. 15.1%) and hypertension (59.8% vs. 39.9%).

Within the follow-up analytic sample, baseline characteristics differed by sex. Men had lower baseline global cognitive function than women (0.20 vs 0.42) and higher prevalence of hypertension (59.1% vs 47.5%) (Table 2, Supplementary figure 3). Educational profiles differed, with women more likely to have primary education, more frequently classified as pensioners not employed and had higher baseline deprivation (1.6 vs 1.2).

Association between PF level and cognitive function (pooled analysis)

In pooled analysis, lower baseline PF was consistently associated with higher odds of lower cognition at follow-up (Table 3). In model 1 (age and sex adjusted), low PF group had double the odds of cognitive decline compared to robust group (OR: 2.03; 95% CI: 1.42 to 2.92). After adding baseline cognitive z-score (Model 2), the association was attenuated but remained increased in the low PF group (OR: 1.71, 95% CI 1.13 to 2.59). In the main multivariable model (Model 3), the estimate for low PF attenuated to OR 1.42 (95% CI 0.91 to 2.21), and after applying IPW (Model 4) it was OR 1.37 (95% CI 0.80 to 2.35) (Supplementary figure 5).

Sex-stratified associations: primary models

Among women (n=691), lower PF at baseline was associated with increased risk of lower cognition over the follow-up period (Table 4). In Model 1 (age-adjusted), those in the good (OR: 1.78, 95% CI 1.16 to 2.73),

moderate (OR: 1.94, 95% CI 1.22 to 3.10), and low (OR: 2.63, 95% CI 1.68 to 4.12) PF categories all had higher odds of lower cognition compared with the robust group. After adjustment for baseline cognition (Model 2), the association remained strong in the low PF group (Model 2: OR: 2.04, 95% CI: 1.22 to 3.41). In the main multivariable model (Model 3) the association was attenuated but the gradient across categories was preserved: good PF OR 1.41 (95% CI 0.84 to 2.35), moderate PF OR 1.61 (95% CI 0.92 to 2.83), and low PF OR 1.53 (95% CI 0.87 to 2.68). Estimates were consistent after applying IPW (Model 4): good PF (OR: 1.47, 95% CI: 0.84 to 2.56), moderate PF (OR: 1.70, 95% CI: 0.92 to 3.15), and low PF (OR: 1.53, 95% CI: 0.80 to 2.90).

In men (n=452), no clear association between baseline PF and follow-up cognition was observed (Table 4). In Model 1, ORs were 1.10 (95% CI 0.63 to 1.93) for good, 0.93 (95% CI 0.53 to 1.65) for moderate, and 1.26 (95% CI 0.68 to 2.35) for low PF. Model 2 estimates were similar: 1.11 (95% CI 0.59 to 2.07), 0.69 (95% CI 0.36 to 1.31), and 1.22 (95% CI 0.59 to 2.50). In the main multivariable model (Model 3), estimates remained non-significant: good PF OR 1.38 (95% CI 0.69 to 2.73), moderate PF OR 0.57 (95% CI 0.28 to 1.16), low PF OR 1.09 (95% CI 0.49 to 2.42). IPW-adjusted estimates (Model 4) were similar.

Sensitivity analyses

Restricting the analysis to incident cases of lower cognition among participants with baseline cognition at or above the median further supported temporality (Supplementary table 2, Figure 2). Among women with preserved baseline cognition (n=482), low PF predicted incident lower cognition, with in age-adjusted OR of 2.19 (95% CI: 1.25 to 3.86) in Model 1. After adjustment for baseline cognition (Model 2), the risk remained increased in the moderate and low PF groups: OR 1.89 (95% CI 1.01 to 3.53) and OR 1.87 (95% CI 1.03 to 3.40), respectively. In the multivariable model (Model 3) and IPW adjusted (Model 4) associations attenuated with larger confidence intervals, likely reflecting selection and attrition effects in the most impaired group together with limited precision due to smaller sample size. Men showed no significant association.

Results using continuous global cognitive scores as the outcome confirmed the pattern observed in binary analyses (Supplementary table 3). In women, age-adjusted models showed a decline in cognitive scores for

those with good PF ($\beta = -0.17$ SD, 95% CI: -0.29 to -0.04), moderate PF ($\beta = -0.19$, 95% CI: -0.32 to -0.05), and low PF ($\beta = -0.32$, 95% CI: -0.46 to -0.18). After additional adjustment for baseline cognition, estimates attenuated and only low PF remained associated with lower follow-up cognition ($\beta = -0.15$, 95% CI -0.26 to -0.05). Similar trend was observed in the multivariable model, low PF ($\beta = -0.07$, 95% CI: -0.18 to 0.04), and in the IPW model, low PF ($\beta = -0.11$, 95% CI: -0.25 to 0.02). In men, baseline PF was not associated with follow-up global cognition in any model.

Using the follow-up median to define cognitive impairment yielded similar results (Supplementary table 4, Supplementary figure 6). Among women in Model 1, ORs were 1.72 (95% CI 1.11 to 2.66) for good, 2.11 (95% CI 1.31 to 3.40) for moderate, and 2.47 (95% CI 1.57 to 3.88) for low PF. In Model 2, the association between PF and cognitive decline remained significant in the moderate (OR 1.75, 95% CI 1.02 to 3.00) and low (OR 1.84, 95% CI 1.10 to 3.07) PF groups. In Model 3, the results were significant in the moderate PF group (OR: 1.77, 95% CI 1.01 to 3.10). In men, associations remained non-significant.

When PF was specified using five categories, the pattern in women was consistent with the main analysis (Supplementary table 5). Five-category PF analyses produced unstable estimates in the very low group, supporting the decision to combine low and very low categories. Additional adjustment for cardiovascular history and depression in fully adjusted models slightly attenuated the estimates in women but preserved the direction and relative magnitude of the associations across PF categories (Supplementary table 6).

When PF was modelled as a continuous variable (per SD increase in the proportion of deficits), in Model 2, the OR for lower cognition in women was 1.25 (95% CI 1.00 to 1.56), while in men the OR was 0.95 (95% CI: 0.65 to 1.38), providing additional support for a dose-response relationship only in women.

Discussion

This prospective study showed that poorer PF in midlife predicted later cognitive decline in women over 20 years of follow-up, while no association was detected in men. Associations in women were dose-dependent across the PF spectrum, remained consistent across sensitivity analyses, including restriction to incident cases among participants with preserved cognition at baseline, different outcome definitions, and after

correcting for selective attrition.

Comparison with previous studies

Previous longitudinal studies examined the association between PF and cognitive outcomes. In cohorts of older adults, slower gait speed, poorer balance, and impaired chair stand performance have been associated with higher dementia risk, with hazard ratios commonly around 1.6 per standard deviation decrease in performance⁸. Lower muscle strength has been linked to increased risk of Alzheimer's disease and more rapid cognitive decline⁹. The motoric cognitive risk syndrome, defined by the combination of slow gait and subjective cognitive complaints, has been associated with more than threefold higher dementia incidence⁷. In the ASPREE trial, slow gait and weak grip strength each predicted dementia and cognitive decline, and their combination was associated with a 79% increase in dementia risk and a 43% increase in risk of cognitive decline over approximately 5 to 7 years¹⁰.

Other longitudinal studies suggest a bidirectional relationship, where physical functioning and cognition each predict decline in the other over time^{5,6}. Physical activity has also been investigated as a predictor of cognitive decline. In the Whitehall II cohort, Sabia et al. reported no association between leisure-time physical activity and cognitive decline or dementia when analyses accounted for prodromal period of dementia¹⁵. In that study, physical activity levels decreased in the years preceding diagnosis, suggesting that associations observed in studies with shorter follow-up may partly reflect reverse causation.

Sex differences in cognitive aging and in PF have been reported in several studies. Women often demonstrate higher cognitive scores in midlife but may experience steeper decline in certain domains in later life^{17,20}. Data from European studies suggest that women report more ADL and IADL limitations than men¹⁶. Cross-national analyses further show that women tend to have better cognitive performance but lower grip strength compared with men²¹. These findings indicate that PF and cognitive aging may follow sex-different patterns.

Evidence on sex differences in associations between PF and cognition in previous studies from diverse populations supported the observed association in our study. A coordinated multi-study analysis across nine

longitudinal cohorts (IALSA network) found that significant longitudinal associations between decline in handgrip strength and cognition were more common in women than in men (23.5% vs 8.8% of cohort-domain combinations)²⁷. In a large cross-sectional study of community-dwelling Japanese older adults (JPSC-AD), a decrease in gait speed was associated with increased risk of cognitive impairment in both sexes, with a stronger association in women (OR: 2.02; 95% CI: 1.47 to 2.76) than in men (OR: 1.75; 95% CI: 1.29 to 2.38) and with the age-related pattern differed by sex²⁸. In the Mayo Clinic Study of Aging, women who were physically inactive in midlife experienced more pronounced decline in global cognition and language than men regardless of activity level, while the association was not observed for late-life activity²⁹. These findings suggest that midlife represents a sensitive window during which PF may have particularly strong associations with cognitive trajectories in women.

The present findings extend earlier cross-sectional HAPIEE study showing that lower PF is associated with cognitive impairment and that associations are stronger in women than in men²². Our Central European cohort adds evidence from a geographic setting that remains underrepresented in cognitive aging research and provides additional evidence on the association between PF and cognition in several aspects. PF was assessed in midlife, at a mean age of approximately 55 years, and cognitive outcomes were measured about 20 years later, extending follow-up beyond that of most previous cohorts⁸⁻¹¹. The PFS used in this analysis incorporates ADL/IADL limitations, grip strength, mobility limitations, and physical activity²², thereby reflecting multiple aspects of functional status rather than a single performance measure. In addition, this study used a sex-stratified approach and found associations in women only, whereas pooled analyses may reduce apparent sex differences.

Reverse causality and sensitivity analysis

Clarifying the temporal relationship between PF and cognition is essential for interpreting these results.

Several aspects of the design and analyses are relevant.

First, baseline assessment at mean age 55, with a 20-year follow-up, falls outside the typical window when

prodromal dementia might influence associations^{14,15}.

Second, adjustment for baseline global cognition changes the meaning of the association between PF and follow-up cognition. Age-adjusted models (Model 1) describe an overall association across PF groups, reflecting both differences present at baseline and change over follow-up. When baseline cognition is included (Model 2 onward), the analysis addresses a narrower question: whether PF remains associated with follow-up cognition among individuals with similar baseline cognitive performance. Baseline cognition is strongly correlated with late-life cognition and with determinants of both PF and cognition such as education and cardiovascular risk³⁰. Attenuation from Model 1 to Model 2 is therefore expected and indicates that baseline cognitive performance accounts for a substantial part of between-person variation in later cognitive outcomes. In women, adding baseline cognition reduced the OR for low PF from OR: 2.63 (95% CI: 1.68 to 4.12) to OR 2.04 (95% CI: 1.22 to 3.41) in the binary outcome, and from β : -0.32 (95% CI: -0.46 to -0.18) to β -0.15 (95% CI: -0.26 to -0.05) in the continuous outcome. Both Model 2 estimates remained statistically significant, indicating that PF provides independent prognostic information beyond baseline cognitive level.

Third, the incident case analysis helps to address concerns about reverse causation. Among women with baseline cognition at or above the median, those with moderate and low PF had approximately twice the odds of developing lower cognition, even after adjustment for baseline cognition. By excluding women with initially low cognitive scores, this analysis reduces the likelihood that associations reflect early cognitive deficits already affecting PF.

Fourth, the consistency of findings across outcome definitions supports the robustness of results. Whether lower cognition was defined using the baseline or follow-up median, or modelled as a continuous outcome, lower baseline PF in women consistently predicted poorer cognitive performance two decades later. Using the baseline median offers a stable reference for decline assessment, while the follow-up median reflects cognitive function among survivors. Continuous modelling maximizes use of available data and avoids threshold-related bias. Consistent results across these methods reduce the likelihood that findings are due to outcome categorization.

Fifth, selective attrition is a major threat in long-term aging studies when both PF and cognition influence dropout and mortality^{26,31}. In our cohort, only 26% of baseline participants completed follow-up, and those lost were older, more often male, and had poorer baseline cognition and PF. This pattern is consistent with healthy survivor bias, which can attenuate associations in complete-case analyses. IPW addresses this by reweighting the observed follow-up sample using baseline predictors of follow-up participation to approximate the baseline population²⁶.

Finally, loss of precision under multivariable adjustment and IPW. The absence of the significant associations in Models 3 and 4 was observed for two reasons. First, each model adds further covariates, increasing complexity and reducing the effect size between PF categories. Second, IPW reweights the observed sample to approximate the baseline cohort, which increases variance when predicted probabilities of follow-up vary across individuals. In addition, a dose-response gradient across PF categories is therefore not expected to be preserved in fully adjusted and weighted models. In women, the moderate PF group estimates in Models 3 and 4 exceeded the low PF group estimate in some analysis. This pattern reflects the fact that PF categories share determinants with outcome-related covariates to different degrees, so the relative magnitude of estimates across categories changes as further covariates are added. Interpretation should therefore be based on the overall pattern of evidence across outcome types, outcome definitions, and modelling strategies rather than on category-level estimates from any single model.

Taken together, these findings demonstrate that poorer PF in midlife predicts later cognitive decline in women, likely reflecting both shared risk factors and direct predictive pathway, rather than being fully explained by early preclinical dementia. However, the observational design and potential for residual confounding limit causal interpretation.

Sex-differences and possible mechanisms

Significant sex differences were observed in the relation between PF and late-life cognition. In women, PF predicted later cognition across binary and continuous outcomes and across multiple modelling approaches, while in men, estimates remained close to null with no consistent association.

Several possible mechanisms may explain these differences. One important factor is the menopausal transition. Women in this cohort were, on average, in their mid-50s at baseline, an age when estrogen levels decline. Estrogen interacts with synaptic plasticity, neurotrophic signalling, mitochondrial function, and inflammatory processes in the brain^{18,19}, as well as muscle mass, bone density, and vascular health^{18,19,32,33}. Reduced levels of estrogen may, therefore, accelerate deterioration in both PF and cognition. In midlife women, lower PF may reflect underlying physiological changes related to estrogen decline that affect both systems, leading to higher risk of later cognitive decline.

Differences in the main causes of limitations between women and men may also be important. Studies suggest that functional limitations in women are more often linked to musculoskeletal conditions such as osteoarthritis and osteoporosis, while in men they more frequently reflect cardiovascular disease and stroke^{32,33}. PFS, which incorporates ADL/IADL, mobility, and grip strength, may therefore be more closely related to musculoskeletal and neuromuscular processes in women, which are themselves linked to brain aging via inflammatory and metabolic pathways. In men, similar PF scores may reflect a wider range of underlying health conditions, some of which are less closely associated with cognitive decline, potentially attenuating a true association.

Selective survival may contribute to the lack of association in men. Men with poor PF and high cardiovascular or neurodegenerative burden may have higher mortality before follow-up, depleting those with higher risk from the analytic sample. Shaw et al. showed via simulation that selective survival can attenuate observed sex differences in dementia incidence³¹. In this study, IPW strengthened associations in women but not in men, supporting impact of sex-specific selection patterns on these findings.

Finally, sex differences in cognitive reserve and physiological response to physical activity may also contribute. Women generally perform better on cognitive tests in midlife and may be more sensitive to certain risk factors such as hypertension in relation to memory decline^{17,20}. Evidence from intervention studies shows that physical activity may provide stronger cognitive benefits, especially for executive function, in women than in men³⁴. These factors may further explain the more consistent association between PF and later cognitive outcomes in women.

Clinical and public health implications

From a clinical and public health perspective, these findings support the use of midlife PF assessment to identify women at higher long-term risk for cognitive decline. The dose-response pattern seen even among participants in the good PF category suggests that prevention may need to start earlier than the stage of apparent limitation. Multidomain prevention strategies that combine physical activity, cognitive training, and vascular risk management have shown benefit in trials, including FINGER, which reported reduced cognitive decline over 2 years³⁵. Our results provide epidemiologic support for targeting midlife women with poorer PF for such approaches, while recognizing that observational evidence cannot establish intervention effects.

Future studies should assess potential mechanisms more directly by examining estrogen-related pathways, neuroinflammatory markers, and vascular function. Repeated measurement of PF and cognition would provide additional evidence, whether menopause is a sensitive window, and whether change in PF add more information than a single baseline measure. Longer-term trials or quasi-experimental studies will be needed to test whether improving PF in midlife reduces later cognitive decline.

Strengths and Limitations

This study's main strength is the long prospective follow-up from midlife into older age. The PFS combines ADL and IADL, grip strength, mobility limitations, and physical activity, providing a multidimensional indicator rather than relying on single-test assessments. The CERAD battery provides standardized cognitive assessment that is comparable across studies. Sensitivity analyses, including adjustment for baseline cognition, restriction to incident cases, continuous outcomes, and alternative cut-points, showed consistent findings. The use of IPW to address selective attrition adds methodological strength relative to many cohort studies with similar follow-up periods.

Several limitations require acknowledgment. First, attrition was substantial (74% loss), and although IPW addresses measured predictors of loss to follow-up, bias from unmeasured determinants may remain.

Second, sample size, in sex-stratified sensitivity analyses, limited precision. Non-significant results in men

should not be interpreted as proof of no association. Third, measurement at only two time points does not allow examination of trajectories over time. Fourth, some PF components relied on self-report, which may be influenced by recall bias. Fifth, the cohort comprised Czech urban residents aged 45–69 years at baseline, which may limit generalizability to other populations. Sixth, residual confounding from unmeasured factors remains possible despite extensive adjustment.

In conclusion, this prospective study provides robust longitudinal evidence that reduced PF at midlife predicted lower cognition in later life in women but not in men. Associations in women were observed across all PF spectrum and were robust to multiple sensitivity analyses and to correction for selective follow-up. These findings support the use of multidomain PF assessment as an early indicator of cognitive decline in women and emphasise the need for sex-stratified approaches in cognitive aging research and dementia prevention.

List of abbreviations

HAPIEE: Health, Alcohol and Psychosocial factors in Eastern Europe

PF: Physical Functioning

PFS: Physical Functioning Score

ADL: Activities of daily living

IADL: Instrumental activities of daily living

CERAD: Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's Disease

CVD: Cardiovascular disease

COPD: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

LASSO: The least absolute shrinkage and selection operator

OR: Odds ratio

SD: standard deviation

CI: confidence interval

Declaration

Ethics approval and consent to participate

All participants provided written informed consent. The study was performed in line with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki. Approval was granted by the Joint UCL/UCLH Committees on the Ethics of Human Research (Committee Alpha), reference 99/0081; Ethics Committee at the National Institute of Public Health, Prague (reference 2002-01-08/P1).

Availability of data and materials

The data used to conduct the research are available from the corresponding author but restrictions by the register maintainers apply to the availability of these data. Therefore, the data are not publicly available. However, data are available from the authors upon reasonable request and with permission of the register maintainers.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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Authors' contributions

All listed authors contributed to the intellectual conceptualisation of this study. TC, HP and MB codesigned the paper. TC performed the statistical analyses. MB, AD and NC jointly designed the HAPIEE study. TC wrote the first draft and finalised the paper. All co-authors provided comments.

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Data statement

The data has not been previously presented orally or by poster at scientific meetings.

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Table 1. Characteristics of the study sample of people according to cognitive status* (n=1 143)

Variables	Higher Cognition (n=489)		Lower Cognition (n=654)		Standardized Difference
Age (years), mean SD	52.7	5.7	56.8	6.3	0.7
Sex, n (%)					0.4
Men	137	(28.0)	315	(48.2)	
Women	352	(72.0)	339	(51.8)	
Education, n (%)					0.5
Primary	15	(3.1)	50	(7.6)	
Secondary	91	(18.6)	228	(34.9)	
Vocational	251	(51.3)	277	(42.4)	
University	132	(27.0)	99	(15.1)	
Occupational status, n (%)					0.6
Employed	387	(79.1)	357	(54.6)	
Retired/employed	22	(4.5)	68	(10.4)	
Retired/unemployed	67	(13.7)	203	(31.0)	
Unemployed	12	(2.5)	18	(2.8)	
Smoking status^a, n (%)					0.1
Never	267	(54.6)	340	(52.0)	
Past smoker	128	(26.2)	165	(25.2)	
Current smoker	93	(19.0)	142	(21.7)	
Alcohol consumption^b, n (%)					0.2
Never	22	(4.5)	47	(7.2)	
<1/monthly	120	(24.5)	172	(26.3)	
1-3/monthly	116	(23.7)	117	(17.9)	
1-4/weekly	179	(36.6)	217	(33.2)	
≥5/weekly	47	(9.6)	92	(14.1)	
Deprivation range ^c , mean (SD)	1.2	1.9	1.6	2.2	0.2
BMI categories^d, n (%)					0.4
Normal	212	(43.4)	149	(22.8)	
Overweight	203	(41.5)	351	(53.7)	
Obese	74	(15.1)	154	(23.5)	
Global cognitive Z-score^e, mean (SD)	0.65	(0.4)	0.10	(0.5)	1.1
Comorbidities, n (%)					
Hypertension	195	(39.9)	391	(59.8)	0.3
Myocardial infarction	5	(1.0)	8	(1.2)	0.0
Ischemic heart disease	8	(1.6)	30	(4.6)	0.2
Stroke	6	(1.2)	13	(2.0)	0.1
COPD	42	(8.6)	74	(11.3)	0.1
Asthma	22	(4.5)	22	(3.4)	0.1
Diabetes	20	(4.1)	46	(7.0)	0.2
Depression	77	(15.7)	127	(19.4)	0.1

BMI, body mass index; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the baseline median of the global cognitive score.

^aSmoking category ((current or past heavy smoker (>30 cigarettes per day), moderate smoker (11 - 29 cigarettes per day), or light smoker (<10 cigarettes per day)).

^bAlcohol consumption (never, graduated frequency from 1-3 drinks monthly or 1-5 drinks weekly).

^cDeprivation scale (graded from 1 as a least deprived up to 12 as a most deprived).

^dBMI categories based on WHO recommendations.

^eAge-, sex- specific composite Z-score of all cognitive tests including episodic memory, verbal fluency and mental speed and concentration tests.

Table 2. Baseline characteristics of the study sample by sex (n = 1,143)

Variables	Men (n=452)		Women (n=691)		Standardized Difference
Age (years), mean SD	55.34	(6.60)	54.86	(6.18)	0.1
PF categories (4 levels), n (%)					0.1
<i>Robust</i>	136	(30.1)	222	(32.1)	
<i>Good</i>	123	(27.2)	178	(25.8)	
<i>Moderate</i>	103	(22.8)	133	(19.2)	
<i>Low</i>	90	(19.9)	158	(22.9)	
Education, n (%)					0.5
<i>Primary</i>	5	(1.1)	60	(8.7)	
<i>Secondary</i>	149	(33.0)	170	(24.6)	
<i>Vocational</i>	177	(39.2)	351	(50.8)	
<i>University</i>	121	(26.8)	110	(15.9)	
Occupational status, n (%)					0.3
<i>Employed</i>	325	(72.9)	419	(60.9)	
<i>Retired/employed</i>	38	(8.5)	52	(7.6)	
<i>Retired/unemployed</i>	71	(15.9)	199	(28.9)	
<i>Unemployed</i>	12	(2.7)	18	(2.6)	
Smoking status^a, n (%)					0.2
<i>Never</i>	221	(49.2)	386	(56.3)	
<i>Past smoker</i>	134	(29.8)	159	(23.2)	
<i>Current smoker</i>	94	(20.9)	141	(20.6)	
Alcohol consumption^b, n (%)					0.7
<i>Never</i>	16	(3.6)	53	(7.8)	
<i><1/monthly</i>	65	(14.6)	227	(33.2)	
<i>1-3/monthly</i>	67	(15.0)	166	(24.3)	
<i>1-4/weekly</i>	196	(43.9)	200	(29.3)	
<i>≥5/weekly</i>	102	(22.9)	37	(5.4)	
Deprivation range ^c , mean (SD)	1.2	2.0	1.6	2.2	0.2
BMI categories^d, n (%)					0.3
<i>Normal</i>	106	(23.5)	255	(36.9)	
<i>Overweight</i>	260	(57.5)	294	(42.5)	
<i>Obese</i>	86	(19.0)	142	(20.5)	
Global cognitive Z-score^e, mean (SD)	0.20	0.6	0.42	0.5	0.4
Comorbidities, n (%)					
<i>Hypertension</i>	267	(59.1)	319	(46.2)	0.3
<i>Myocardial infarction</i>	8	(1.8)	5	(0.7)	0.0
<i>Ischemic heart disease</i>	20	(4.5)	18	(2.7)	0.1
<i>Stroke</i>	11	(2.5)	8	(1.2)	0.1
<i>COPD</i>	44	(9.9)	72	(10.7)	0.0
<i>Asthma</i>	8	(1.8)	36	(5.4)	0.1
<i>Diabetes</i>	25	(5.5)	41	(6.0)	0.1
<i>Depression</i>	62	(13.7)	142	(20.5)	0.2

BMI, body mass index; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

^aSmoking category ((current or past heavy smoker (>30 cigarettes per day), moderate smoker (11 - 29 cigarettes per day), or light smoker (<10 cigarettes per day)).

^bAlcohol consumption (never, graduated frequency from 1-3 drinks monthly or 1-5 drinks weekly).

^cDeprivation scale (graded from 1 as a least deprived up to 12 as a most deprived).

^dBMI categories based on WHO recommendations.

^eAge-, sex- specific composite Z-score of all cognitive tests including episodic memory, verbal fluency and mental speed and concentration tests.

Table 3. Pooled association between level of PF and risk of lower cognition at follow-up* (n=1 143).

	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 4 OR [#] (95% CI)
<i>PF Categories</i>					
<i>Robust</i>	358	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	301	1.49 (1.06-2.08)	1.34 (0.92-1.96)	1.42 (0.95-2.11)	1.32 (0.87-2.01)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	236	1.46 (1.02-2.09)	1.13 (0.75-1.70)	1.08 (0.70-1.66)	1.09 (0.69-1.71)
<i>Low PF</i>	248	2.03 (1.42-2.92)	1.71 (1.13-2.59)	1.42 (0.91-2.21)	1.37 (0.80-2.35)

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the baseline median of the global cognitive score.

[§]Model 1 = Adjusted for age, sex

[†]Model 2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3 = Model 2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

[#]Model 4 = Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

Table 4. Sex-stratified associations between level of PF and risk of lower cognition at follow-up* (n=1 143).

	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 4 OR [#] (95% CI)
Women (n=691)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	222	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	178	1.78 (1.16-2.73)	1.49 (0.92-2.43)	1.41 (0.84-2.35)	1.47 (0.84-2.56)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	133	1.94 (1.22-3.10)	1.59 (0.93-2.72)	1.61 (0.92-2.83)	1.70 (0.92-3.15)
<i>Low PF</i>	158	2.63 (1.68-4.12)	2.04 (1.22-3.41)	1.53 (0.87-2.68)	1.53 (0.80-2.90)
Men (n=452)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	136	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	123	1.10 (0.63-1.93)	1.11 (0.59-2.07)	1.38 (0.69-2.73)	1.27 (0.63-2.56)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	103	0.93 (0.53-1.65)	0.69 (0.36-1.31)	0.57 (0.28-1.16)	0.56 (0.28-1.11)
<i>Low PF</i>	90	1.26 (0.68-2.35)	1.22 (0.59-2.50)	1.09 (0.49-2.42)	1.06 (0.36-3.09)

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the baseline median of the global cognitive score.

[§]Model 1 = Adjusted for age

[†]Model 2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3 = Model 2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

[#]Model 4 = Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Flowchart of exclusion criteria of the HAPIEE study cohort.

Figure 2. Sex-stratified associations between baseline PF categories and incident lower cognition at 20-year follow-up, restricted to participants with baseline cognition at or above the median (n = 720: 482 women, 238 men).

Supplementary Table 1. Characteristics of the study sample of people according by follow-up availability (n=4 396)

Variables	No follow-up data (n=3 253)		Included in the follow-up (n=1 143)		Standardized Difference
Age (years), mean SD	59.59	(6.97)	55.05	(6.35)	0.6
Sex, n (%)					0.4
Men	1 539	(47.3)	452	(39.5)	
Women	1 714	(52.7)	691	(60.5)	
PF categories (4 levels), n (%)					0.3
<i>Robust</i>	752	(23.1)	358	(31.3)	
<i>Good</i>	745	(22.9)	301	(26.3)	
<i>Moderate</i>	665	(20.4)	236	(20.6)	
<i>Low</i>	1 091	(33.5)	248	(21.7)	
Education, n (%)					0.4
<i>Primary</i>	370	(11.5)	65	(5.7)	
<i>Secondary</i>	1241	(38.4)	319	(27.9)	
<i>Vocational</i>	1 184	(36.7)	528	(46.2)	
<i>University</i>	434	(13.4)	231	(20.2)	
Occupational status, n (%)					0.6
<i>Employed</i>	1 195	(37.1)	744	(65.6)	
<i>Retired/employed</i>	294	(9.1)	90	(7.9)	
<i>Retired/unemployed</i>	1 643	(51.0)	270	(23.8)	
<i>Unemployed</i>	91	(2.8)	30	(2.6)	
Smoking status^a, n (%)					0.2
<i>Never</i>	1 457	(45.3)	607	(53.5)	
<i>Past smoker</i>	973	(30.3)	293	(25.8)	
<i>Current smoker</i>	783	(24.4)	235	(20.7)	
Alcohol consumption^b, n (%)					0.3
<i>Never</i>	351	(11.2)	69	(6.1)	
<i><1/monthly</i>	829	(26.4)	292	(25.9)	
<i>1-3/monthly</i>	697	(22.2)	233	(20.6)	
<i>1-4/weekly</i>	847	(27.0)	396	(35.1)	
<i>≥5/weekly</i>	417	(13.3)	139	(12.3)	
Deprivation range ^c , mean (SD)	1.6	2.2	1.4	2.1	0.0
BMI categories^d, n (%)					0.3
Normal	748	(23.0)	361	(31.6)	
Overweight	1 442	(44.3)	554	(48.5)	
Obese	1 058	(32.5)	228	(19.9)	
Global cognitive Z-score^e, mean (SD)	0.03	(0.68)	0.33	(0.56)	0.5
Comorbidities, n (%)					
<i>Hypertension</i>	2 202	(67.8)	586	(51.3)	0.3
<i>Myocardial infarction</i>	165	(5.3)	13	(1.2)	0.3
<i>Ischemic heart disease</i>	265	(8.5)	38	(3.4)	0.2
<i>Stroke</i>	105	(3.4)	19	(1.7)	0.2
<i>COPD</i>	475	(15.2)	116	(10.4)	0.1
<i>Asthma</i>	140	(4.5)	44	(3.9)	0.1
<i>Diabetes</i>	370	(11.4)	66	(5.8)	0.2
<i>Depression</i>	708	(21.8)	204	(17.8)	0.1

BMI, body mass index; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

^aSmoking category ((current or past heavy smoker (>30 cigarettes per day), moderate smoker (11 - 29 cigarettes per day), or light smoker (<10 cigarettes per day)).

^bAlcohol consumption (never, graduated frequency from 1-3 drinks monthly or 1-5 drinks weekly).

^cDeprivation scale (graded from 1 as a least deprived up to 12 as a most deprived).

^dBMI categories based on WHO recommendations.

^eAge-, sex- specific composite Z-score of all cognitive tests including episodic memory, verbal fluency and mental speed and concentration tests.

Supplementary figure 1

a. PFS distribution by follow-up availability.

b. Cognitive function distribution by follow-up availability.

Supplementary figure 2

a. Baseline cognitive function by PF group

b. Follow-up cognitive function by PF group

c. Follow-up participation by PF group

Supplementary figure 3.

a. Baseline cognitive function distribution by sex.

b. Follow-up cognitive function distribution by sex.

c. Cognitive impairment distribution by PF categories and sex.

Supplementary figure 4.

a. IPW weight distribution by PF category (4 levels).

b. IPW weight distribution by PF category (5 levels).

Supplementary figure 5.

a. Unweighted probabilities of cognitive impairment by PF.

b. IPW weighted probabilities of cognitive impairment by PF

Supplementary figure 6.

a. Proportion with cognitive impairment at follow-up (f-up vs fixed cut point).

b. Cognitive impairment at follow-up (f-up vs fixed cut point) by PFS

Supplementary Table 2. Sex-stratified associations between level of PF and risk of incident lower cognition at follow-up* restricted to participants with baseline cognition at or above the baseline median (n=720).

	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 4 OR [#] (95% CI)
Women (n=482)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	168	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	128	1.73 (1.02-2.92)	1.28 (0.73-2.24)	1.21 (0.66-2.19)	1.18 (0.64-2.19)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	91	2.04 (1.15-3.63)	1.89 (1.01-3.53)	1.78 (0.92-3.46)	1.59 (0.80-3.18)
<i>Low PF</i>	95	2.19 (1.25-3.86)	1.87 (1.03-3.40)	1.23 (0.64-2.38)	1.06 (0.52-2.18)
Men (n=238)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	75	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	69	1.02 (0.51-2.05)	1.00 (0.49-2.05)	1.29 (0.57-2.92)	1.37 (0.58-3.21)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	50	0.70 (0.33-1.49)	0.63 (0.29-1.39)	0.51 (0.20-1.30)	0.52 (0.21-1.31)
<i>Low PF</i>	44	1.25 (0.57-2.76)	1.27 (0.55-2.90)	1.25 (0.48-3.25)	1.83 (0.64-5.23)

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the baseline median of the global cognitive score.

[§]Model 1 = Adjusted for age

[†]Model 2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3 = Model 2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

[#]Model 4 = Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

Supplementary Table 3. Sex-stratified associations between level of PF and continuous cognitive function at follow-up (n=1 143).

	No. of persons	Model 1 β^s (95% CI)	Model 2 β^+ (95% CI)	Model 3 β^\ddagger (95% CI)	Model 4 $\beta^\#$ (95% CI)
Women (n=691)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	222	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Good PF</i>	178	-0.17 (-0.29, -0.04)	-0.06 (-0.16, 0.05)	-0.04 (-0.14, 0.06)	-0.06 (-0.18, 0.05)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	133	-0.19 (-0.32, -0.05)	-0.09 (-0.20, 0.03)	-0.07 (-0.19, 0.04)	-0.10 (-0.25, 0.04)
<i>Low PF</i>	158	-0.32 (-0.46, -0.18)	-0.15 (-0.26, -0.05)	-0.07 (-0.18, 0.04)	-0.11 (-0.25, 0.02)
Men (n=452)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	136	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
<i>Good PF</i>	123	-0.01 (-0.17, 0.15)	-0.01 (-0.15, 0.12)	-0.05 (-0.18, 0.09)	-0.06 (-0.23, 0.11)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	103	0.05 (-0.13, 0.23)	0.04 (-0.10, 0.19)	0.06 (-0.09, 0.20)	0.03 (-0.13, 0.18)
<i>Low PF</i>	90	-0.09 (-0.25, 0.08)	-0.04 (-0.17, 0.10)	-0.02 (-0.15, 0.12)	-0.01 (-0.16, 0.14)

CI, confidence interval; β , mean difference in follow-up continuous cognitive function (SD) compared with the robust PF group (negative values indicate lower follow-up cognition).

^sModel 1 = Adjusted for age

⁺Model 2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3 = Model 2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

[#]Model 4 = Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

Supplementary Table 4. Sex-stratified associations between level of PF and risk of lower cognition at follow-up* using the follow-up median cut point (n=1 143).

	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 4 OR [#] (95% CI)
Women (n=691)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	222	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	178	1.72 (1.11-2.66)	1.40 (0.85-2.30)	1.32 (0.79-2.21)	1.47 (0.85-2.52)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	133	2.11 (1.31-3.40)	1.75 (1.02-3.00)	1.77 (1.01-3.10)	1.71 (0.90-3.26)
<i>Low PF</i>	158	2.47 (1.57-3.88)	1.84 (1.10-3.07)	1.43 (0.81-2.52)	1.33 (0.70-2.53)
Men (n=452)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	136	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	123	0.88 (0.52-1.49)	0.84 (0.47-1.51)	0.99 (0.51-1.89)	0.97 (0.48-1.96)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	103	1.07 (0.62-1.86)	0.86 (0.47-1.58)	0.67 (0.34-1.33)	0.67 (0.34-1.32)
<i>Low PF</i>	90	1.14 (0.63-2.04)	1.03 (0.53-2.01)	0.91 (0.43-1.92)	0.90 (0.36-2.29)

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the follow-up median of the global cognitive score.

[§]Model 1 = Adjusted for age

[†]Model 2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3 = Model 2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

[#]Model 4 = Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

Supplementary Table 5. Sex-stratified associations between 5 level of PF and risk of lower cognition at follow-up* (n=1 143).

	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 4 OR [#] (95% CI)
Women (n=691)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	222	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	178	1.78 (1.16-2.73)	1.49 (0.92-2.43)	1.41 (0.84-2.35)	1.47 (0.84-2.56)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	133	1.94 (1.22-3.10)	1.59 (0.93-2.73)	1.61 (0.92-2.83)	1.70 (0.92-3.15)
<i>Low PF</i>	125	2.70 (1.67-4.37)	2.07 (1.19-3.59)	1.58 (0.87-2.86)	1.71 (0.91-3.23)
<i>Very Low PF</i>	33	2.38 (1.06-5.39)	1.95 (0.76-4.98)	1.32 (0.46-3.74)	1.04 (0.28-3.79)
Men (n=452)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	136	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	123	1.10 (0.63-1.93)	1.11 (0.59-2.07)	1.38 (0.69-2.73)	1.27 (0.63-2.57)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	103	0.93 (0.53-1.65)	0.69 (0.36-1.31)	0.57 (0.28-1.17)	0.56 (0.28-1.11)
<i>Low PF</i>	81	1.24 (0.65-2.36)	1.21 (0.58-2.52)	1.11 (0.49-2.51)	1.00 (0.30-3.36)
<i>Very Low PF</i>	9	1.44 (0.27-7.74)	1.39 (0.15-13.1)	0.86 (0.06-12.42)	2.01 (0.43-9.41)

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the baseline median of the global cognitive score.

[§]Model 1 = Adjusted for age

[†]Model2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3= Model 2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities.

[#]Model 4= Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

Supplementary Table 6. Sex-stratified associations between level of PF and risk of lower cognition at follow-up* fully adjusted (n=1 143).

	No. of persons	Model 1 OR [§] (95% CI)	Model 2 OR [†] (95% CI)	Model 3 OR [‡] (95% CI)	Model 4 OR [#] (95% CI)
Women (n=691)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	222	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	178	1.78 (1.16-2.73)	1.49 (0.92-2.43)	1.38 (0.82-2.30)	1.44 (0.83-2.50)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	133	1.94 (1.22-3.10)	1.59 (0.93-2.72)	1.54 (0.87-2.73)	1.65 (0.88-3.08)
<i>Low PF</i>	158	2.63 (1.68-4.12)	2.04 (1.22-3.41)	1.46 (0.82-2.59)	1.44 (0.74-2.80)
Men (n=452)					
PF Categories					
<i>Robust</i>	136	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
<i>Good PF</i>	123	1.10 (0.63-1.93)	1.11 (0.59-2.07)	1.37 (0.68-2.76)	1.31 (0.65-2.65)
<i>Moderate PF</i>	103	0.93 (0.53-1.65)	0.69 (0.36-1.31)	0.63 (0.30-1.32)	0.65 (0.33-1.30)
<i>Low PF</i>	90	1.26 (0.68-2.35)	1.22 (0.59-2.50)	1.03 (0.45-2.34)	0.94 (0.31-2.84)

CI, confidence interval; OR, odds ratio.

*Participants were classified as having "lower cognition" at follow-up if their follow-up global cognitive score fell below the baseline median of the global cognitive score.

[§]Model 1 = Adjusted for age

[†]Model2 = Model 1 + Adjusted for baseline global cognitive z-score.

[‡]Model 3= Model2 + Adjusted for occupation, education; alcohol consumption, smoking status; bmi and comorbidities + myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease, stroke, and depression.

[#]Model 4= Model 3 IPW adjusted uses stabilized weights for follow-up participation.

